

THE 'RESOURCE CURSE' AND CONFLICTS IN AFRICA

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Introduction

On what has become widely known as the 'resource curse', high value natural resources have been linked to armed conflicts and instability and lost opportunities for development. In many resource-rich countries, revenues from natural resources—oil, natural gas, minerals, gemstones, timber and others—constitute an important and integral (even dominant) component of national Gross Domestic Product (Bruch et al 2011). In conflict or post conflict countries of Angola, Sudan and Algeria, gas and oil account for well over 60 percent of government

income and over 90 percent of revenues gained from exports. Sierra Leone is well known for both its civil war (which ended in 2002), and the export of diamonds to finance the war. After the conflict, diamonds accounted for approximately 96 percent of all exports for the country (IMF, 2009). For Chad, Libya and Nigeria, countries which have struggled with resource-related conflicts for some time, gas and oil have accounted for as much as 70 percent of the GDP, and over 80 percent of government revenues (Lujala and Rustad, 2012b). Gold and uranium are important in Niger, oil is important in Ivory Coast,

and timber and diamonds provide significant revenues in the Central African Republic.

When well-managed, the natural resources sector can be important in financing development. However, when mismanaged, revenues from these resources can significantly weaken economies and governance, and greatly increase the risk of violence. Figure 1. Presents nine resource rich and conflict prone African countries while Figure 2 presents types of resource conflicts, causes, and manifestations.

Figure 1. The economic role of the natural resource extractive sector in primarily conflict-affected African countries. Source: Lujala and Rustad (2012b).

Figure 2.

A typology of natural resources and conflict causes for Africa. Source Alao (2007).

Money from resource exploitation frequently encourages and fuels corruption, rent seeking and patronage, which can encourage the actions and interests of a relatively small, powerful and predatory elite.

Natural resources vs. national resources

There are three broad types of ‘resource nationalism’: production country nationalism; consumer country nationalism; and investment target country nationalism (Ward, 2009). The first two, are the most relevant to Africa. Production country resource nationalism refers to the “increasing use of control of natural resources to advance policy goals—both economic and foreign” (Stanislaw, 2008). Production country resource nationalism can also refer to:

- a production country seeking to make maximum use and value of its natural resource endowment (MEES, 2006)
- an arrangement where resource producer countries move to maximize revenue from present resource production while changing terms of investment for future output,
- a set of policies and justifications given to policies that increase government intervention in resource development (Ait-Laoussine, 2008); and
- the nationalization of natural resource infrastructure investments made by non-state commercial interests (Stevens and Pearce, 2000).

Consumer country nationalism involves non-resource producer countries or commercial interests attempt-

ing to take control of the sources of natural resources in other countries (Ward, 2009). In extreme cases, this form of resource nationalism can lead to armed conflict (Ward, 2009; Williams, 2009). Investment target country nationalism involves the strategic use of sovereign wealth funds. In this case, revenues are directed toward such funds, often controlled in part or in whole by outside interests (Ward, 2009).

Because high value resources like minerals and oil are usually not distributed evenly across the landscape of a country, different stakeholder groups or constituencies will be advantaged or disadvantaged in the exploitation of these resources, depending on the model of natural resource governance deployed. For example, the people of the Niger Delta occupy land rich in oil but have long felt ‘disadvantaged’ and excluded from the benefits associated with oil extraction, given the way this resource has been managed in Nigeria. Likewise, the indigenous occupants of areas containing diamonds in Sierra Leone suffered dislocation and violence as outside interests sought to gain access to diamond areas. Inequalities, divisiveness, and civil conflicts can emerge if issues of equity, ownership and management of natural resources are not adequately addressed. When the distribution of

resources coincides with ‘tribal’, clan, ethnic, linguistic, religious, class, power and other divisions within society, significant problems associated with real or perceived resource capture can emerge.

The conflict in Niger is partly attributable to management of mineral resources. The Tuareg, on whose lands the minerals and the mines reside, have had significant problems with national governments which they perceive as diverting too much revenue from minerals extracted from their lands to the national capital at the expense of their own regional development. In other cases, those with the instruments of state or economic power in their control may be reluctant to share income and benefits with poorer areas of the country. It is not surprising then that many countries in Africa endowed with high value natural resources have been plagued by civil conflicts.

Resources vs. rights

The (property) rights systems under which natural resources are extracted matters a great deal to a country’s economic prospects, social peace and political stability. Different national legal and legislative frameworks have employed different models in terms of rights acquisition and rights maintenance for various investors (Borras

and Franco, 2010; Corbera et al., 2011). The purpose of the investment can be important in relation to acquisition of rights. For example, in the context of concessions as a form of land rights acquisition, such rights frequently have attached to them the prospect that they can be revoked if the implementation of the investment project does not comply with the stated purpose of the investment, as Mozambique has done.

Some resources are more easily exploited than others and so require less in the way of investment or time, and therefore can involve different kinds of rights than would longer-term investments. For example, timber extraction as an investment is relatively short-term and arguably easier to accomplish than forms of mineral extraction involving heavy equipment, facilities and excavation. It is common, however, for an investor to pursue multiple money-making opportunities based on a specific concession or right to extract a specific resource. If only mining rights are granted in a concession, but forest areas need to be cleared so that mining can take place, then money can be made from timber. If areas within the mining concession are unused for mining operations but can be used for plantations, then revenue can be generated in that way as well. The prospect of being able to pursue money-making opportunities within the area acquired for a specific purpose can lead to exploitation of lands well outside of the rights granted – and/or attempts to expand rights ‘on the ground’ in order to do this. Rights given for mineral, timber, or other extraction activities often do not include the right to exclude local communities from the concession area. However, as enforcement and monitoring capacities on the part of the state remain low in a number of African countries, investors often attempt to engage in exclusionary practices, so as to pursue a variety of revenue streams that were not part of the initial concession or rights (e.g. Yasmi et al., 2010).

The transfer of land resource rights to investors in Africa illustrates many of these problems. Despite widespread individualization, registration, and

privatization of holdings on the one hand, and increasing recognition of informally held rights on the other, the overwhelming majority of high value natural resources in African countries are officially owned and administered by national governments (Corbera et al., 2011; Hallam, 2011). Although a number of contracts involve outright purchases and/or lease agreements with private individuals and institutions, the vast majority of approved and pending contracts involve long-term concessions of state owned lands--although such lands can also be claimed by customary groups. There are two reasons for this. First, land laws in many African countries often restrict (if not prohibit) private ownership of resources ‘in the ground’ by foreign or domestic individuals and organizations. Second, long-term lease agreements with state agencies can reduce the social, political and economic risks associated with acquiring large tracts of land in foreign economies, while simultaneously providing sufficient collateral to guarantee funding and to facilitate the acquisition process (Andrianirina-Ratsialonana et al., 2011; Vermulen and Cotula, 2011).

Beyond the significant gaps in available information on the contracts between investors and public or private landholders, a key challenge to summarizing the nature of the rights obtained is the sheer number of options available. Indeed, large-scale land resource acquisitions are not limited to a specific duration, number of actors or transfer of specific rights. Rather, contracts often ‘mix and match’ different resource tenure arrangements for different pieces of land as part of the same project (Cotula, 2011; Cotula and Mayers, 2011). Furthermore, Cotula and Mayers (2011) demonstrate that joint equity arrangements and multi-party lease schemes offer potential alternatives to current deals between investors, governments and informal land users. Although a large amount of recent literature focuses on the evolution of contracts between different actors and investors (e.g., Ping and Nielsen, 2010), the majority of areas generally fall within and across three main categories, 1) purchase of ownership right; 2) lease/

concession from local land user or institution; and 3) lease/concession from the state (Nelson et al, 2012).

Natural resources – (under)development - conflict

Overdependence on natural resources can adversely affect a country’s economy by exposing it to the risk of severe price shocks. When combined with political and economic institutional weaknesses, such shocks can have disproportionately large negative impacts – sometimes exposing countries to risks of armed conflicts. Positive shocks--as with large windfalls generated from easily extracted natural resources--sometimes destabilize economies as well, leading to missed opportunities (Collier and Hoeffler, 2012), or to overspending, poor investment decisions, and ill-conceived economic policies.

Studies have shown that oil increases the probability of armed conflict (Fearon and Laitin, 2003), and that co-location of gas and oil with conflict is associated with longer running and more severe conflicts (Lujala, 2009). These studies suggest that developing countries that are oil producing are between 1.5 to 2 times more likely to engage in armed conflict than countries without oil; and that where conflict occurs in an area containing oil, conflict can last twice as long and result in double the combatant deaths than it would otherwise (Lujala, 2010). Fearon (2004) has shown that gemstones have effects similar to those of oil—namely, conflict is more likely and tends to last longer. However it should be kept in mind that such statistical studies only demonstrate association, not causation.

Trans boundary conflicts related to natural resource exploitation deserve mention as a separate category: Liberia - Sierra Leone with regard to diamonds and forests (Alao, 2007; Richards, 2001) ; the DRC, and neighboring countries particularly to the east over mineral resources (NATO, 2012); Sudan and South Sudan, over oil (Newnham, 2012); Western Sahara and Morocco over potash mining (Gianadda and de Brito, 2012; Ciment and Waskey, 2007); and what have come to known as ‘water

wars' involving transboundary water-courses, particularly the Nile and the Nile states (Alao, 2007; Klare 2001). Such conflicts can require a different approach, because they often involve neighboring states and their standing armies together with supported proxy militias and movements. Often such conflicts are not about the location of borders but rather how (and by who) access to resources are acquired.

What is most notable about these linkages however is their variation, and their operation at different scales? At the broad scale, easily extractable natural resources or agricultural products (rubber, bananas, cacao, etc.) can provide insurgents with the motives and the means to challenge the state, with the state's own lack of capacity (institutional and military) serving to increase the incentive to do so. Other broad scale linkages include:

- 1) a government able to finance the national budget exclusively or almost exclusively through revenues from natural resources, as opposed to public taxation, can then very easily become disconnected from the general population, and hence is less accountable to it.
- 2) political and economic underperformance--which is common in developing countries endowed with valuable natural resources— can make countries vulnerable to conflict as a pre-existing condition. Several studies show that low state capacity and dysfunctional institutions are positively correlated with an increased likelihood of conflict

(Lujala and Runstad, 2012b).

- 3) A number of African countries (but certainly not all) with an abundance of specific natural resources, such as oil, gas, and certain minerals, have lower economic growth and lower human development than countries where these resources are scarce or absent (Auty, 1993; Karl, 1997). One fairly common explanation for this is that natural resources are not themselves revenues but instead assets. For example oil is an asset within the natural endowment of a country, and when it is taken out of the ground and sold (commercialized) it is simply converted into a liquid asset (Radon, 2007). But the transaction is not revenue, instead it is just a change in the designation of the asset from barrels of oil to U.S. dollars. Therefore the challenge for developing country governments is to be able to transform natural resource based assets into enduring development while not diminishing the assets themselves. But such transformation can be set back by negative incentives created by natural resources--tempting leaders to overspend; seeing revenues as prizes that different groups or segments of society or government attempt to capture, either by corruption or armed confrontation (Alao 2007; Humphreys, et al, 2007).
- 4) Rentier states can be fostered, in which governments rely on revenue from their natural resources, as opposed to revenues generated from their population's produc-

tive activities. Such rentier states are characterized by state-society relations that are weak, and by an authoritarian government that provides undue capacity to government and certain elites (while denying this capacity to others) in order to capture resources (Ottaway, 2003).

At the mid to smaller scale there are numerous linkages between specific resources and conflict. Money from resource exploitation frequently encourages and fuels corruption, rent seeking and patronage, which can encourage the actions and interests of a relatively small, powerful and predatory elite. Often this elite is quite small compared to the national population. For example in Nigeria one estimation indicates that only one percent of the population has control over 80 percent of oil revenues (Kalu, 2008). Stakeholders involved in the 'resource - development with poverty - conflict' trichotomy who have an interest in seeing conflict resolution efforts fail are known as 'spoilers' (Stedman, 1997). Spoilers usually have something to lose from a change in the status quo, either politically or economically. The stakes can be quite significant when high-value resources are involved. When potential spoilers are in positions of power and the gains are large, the temptation to spoil a conflict resolution process for example can be significant (Rustad et al, 2012).

A variety of circumstances can en-

courage spoiling. Stakeholders who have unrealistic expectations about the revenues or benefits associated with resource extraction, their connection to the process, and the speed with which benefits can be delivered can be particularly susceptible to spoiler temptations. Certain groups may wish to engage in spoiler activity out of resentment at being left out of a revenue and/or benefit stream. Others may refuse to participate in a more equitable resource sharing process either because they benefit from the current arrangement or because they see any new arrangement as a threat to the revenue provided by 'lootable' resources (Rustad et al, 2012).

Factionalism is a common problem in armed conflict, whereby certain factions may continue to seek better arrangements for their group (Rustad et al, 2012). As well the 'copycat effect' can be a problem; whereby peace agreements (which often include resource use and access arrangements) aim to deliver benefits to specific factions, who are then 'copied' by other groups who act or pose as factions because they desire access to resources as well. Some factions can come into existence for precisely this reason (Rustad et al, 2012). Liberia is an example of this. Between 1990 and 1995, twelve peace agreements failed. Abuja II, the thirteenth agreement, signed in 1996, was somewhat more successful, but the conflict did not end until 2003, with the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (Dupuy and Detzel, forthcoming). Among the various reasons that led to the failure of successive peace agreements were this copycat effect, and a related pattern whereby factions would sign a peace agreement (with significant international pressure), but then return to their previous ways of resource exploitation under different names, or through splinter groups. This maneuver would then avoid officially breaching the peace agreement (Rustad et al, 2012; Reno, 1999).

Gaining a commitment to stop certain forms of resource exploitation by spoilers can necessitate significant political concessions, involving for example the allocation of ministerial posts, authority over some segments

of the natural resource sector, or allocation of certain land areas (Rustad et al, 2012). Such concessions are often made to encourage factions to join a peace process and transform them into political actors or movements (Rustad et al, 2012). Sierra Leone is an example of this, with part of the 1999 Lomé Peace Agreement, stipulating that Foday Sankoh, the leader of the Revolutionary United Front (RUF), was to be appointed as the head of the Commission for the Management of Strategic Resources, National Reconstruction and Development, and giving him the status of vice president (Binningsbø and Dupuy, 2009). In Angola, the 1994 Lusaka Protocol provided the UNITA insurgency with appointments at the ministerial level, including the ministry responsible for mining (Rustad et al, 2012).

Small-scale stakeholders: implications for management

Small-scale stakeholders are primary actors in the 'natural resources - development with poverty - conflict' trichotomy, and are the focus of much international attention in the context of the resource curse. While there is an array of problems associated with small-scale resource extraction, there are also opportunities. In general 'artisanal and small-scale mining' (ASM) is practiced by basic, manual extraction techniques. It is mostly unregulated, and those that engage in extraction are exposed to a various physical hazards (Hayes and Perks, 2012). It is also associated with numerous economic and social problems--diversion of livelihoods from more sustainable activities; squalid camp conditions where substance abuse and sexual promiscuity create health risks; child labor; environmental damage; and localized inflation (Hayes and Perks, 2012).

As currently practiced in a number of resource rich African countries ASM is poorly done because the technical capacity required to identify, plan, develop, and exploit high value resources to their actual potential does not exist. As a result, small-scale stakeholder extractive activities fails to take full advantage of the overall value of the resource while at the same time consuming or contaminating other

resources—such as wood and other forest resources, land, and water—which are essential to livelihoods particularly once the extractable resource is exhausted. Thus as currently conducted in many countries, ASM may deliver short-term monetary gains to miners and traders who are involved directly, but it may also worsen local poverty for those who are the 'diggers' and who receive very little in the way of compensation. In the DRC, ASM has been linked with armed conflict where minerals extracted by artisanal workers were used to purchase weapons and fund other aspects of the conflict (Hayes and Perks, 2012).

With regard to women's role in small-scale resource extraction, a study in DRC found that their involvement in ASM was for the most part driven by poverty. The study demonstrated that during the years after the conflict in DRC, women's participation in ASM increased as a consequence of the general economic downturn and decreased livelihood opportunities in traditional sectors, such as agriculture. As a result 75 percent of the women studied had been mining for less than two years, and 70 percent were their families' sole earners (Pact, 2007). Nonetheless artisanal mining has become an important source of livelihood for women in resource rich African countries because of its relative ease of entry compared with other sectors, because it requires almost no formal education, skills, or capital. In this regard ASM can provide impoverished women with economic opportunities that might not otherwise exist (Hayes and Perks, 2012).

Thus there is a need to acknowledge the large importance of small-scale resource exploitation for local livelihoods, and to examine the tensions and stresses that can come about from small-scale extraction activities, overlapping claims to the same resources, or to different resources in the same area. In a number of resource-rich African countries, small-scale extraction of high-value natural resources (diamonds, forest and wildlife products, etc.) may be long-established before any conflict, or well prior to the arrival of large-scale extraction interests. As well small-scale exploitation activities

It is thought that if young men remain in the cities, rootless and unemployed, they may become recruits for future militia interests

may develop as a coping strategy during conflict. Such exploitation—often unofficial and/or illegal—can often be the economic backbone of impoverished, or war-torn communities. Local populations hence may view any disruption of their livelihoods—through attempts to stop their small-scale extractive activities, or competition with large-scale exploitation—as a negative development. Economic development of resources that undergird local livelihoods should focus on formalizing and supporting the resource economies on which conflict-affected populations depend (Lujala and Rustad, 2012a). This should include legalizing forms of ASM, so that it is not acted against by the state.

At the same time, large-scale stakeholders themselves figure prominently in the local community setting. Often, large-scale interests are better equipped, organized, and capable than state authorities at the local level. Particularly in post-conflict areas, state organizations and institutions may barely function and so deliver few, if any services such as education, health, and security—whereas

the large-scale interest will be very present with comparatively high capacity, infrastructure assets, and finances. In such circumstances, local community members may not only expect the company to step in for the state in providing needed services, but may transfer their grievances against the state to the company if they fail to provide (Anderson and Zandvliet, 2001).

One of the questions facing resource rich African countries is how to most effectively use a combination of small-scale / large-scale extraction approaches in the pursuit of development objectives. In this context while mineral deposits that are deep in the ground can only be exploited by industrial-scale mining (and foreign capital); other deposits are closer to or on the surface and therefore are much more accessible through small-scale, semi-industrial mining. Still other deposits cannot justify major industrial investment due to their remoteness or the small scale of the deposits, and so are only suitable for manual extraction (Hayes and Perks, 2012). As a result, deriving, regularizing and for-

malizing the right mix of approaches to natural resource exploitation can support exploitation objectives as well as local livelihoods for those who work in the small-scale extractive sector (Hayes and Perks, 2012). Thus for countries endowed with resources that can be exploited by the small-scale extractive sector, such extraction can be regarded as an opportunity rather than as a localized problem (Hayes and Perks, 2012). To attempt to thwart such an opportunity in order to control all deposits can lead to its own set of problems. In a case from Sierra Leone, President Siaka Stevens (1968 - 1985), set his country on the road to prolonged conflict and state failure, in part by centralizing state control of all diamond mining. This worsened already problematic and inequitable land relationships for smallholders and made small-scale diamond mining, on which many Sierra Leoneans relied for their livelihoods, illegal (Beevers, 2012)

It is important to look not only at the negative aspects of the relationship between small and large-scale interests, but the potential positive aspects

as well. For example, large extraction projects usually encourage migration on the part of those wishing to engage in small-scale extraction. And while migration can have destabilizing effects by putting pressure on resources, facilities, local social structures and services, and become a burden or obstacle to be dealt with by commercial companies, in some cases migration can contribute to stability. In Sierra Leone many people would like to see new large-scale investments being made in mining (or in other sectors, such as biofuel), which would draw young men back to their villages of origin, where they can take up employment in resource extraction projects. It is thought that if young men remain in the cities, rootless and unemployed, they may become recruits for future militia interests (Hayes and Perks, 2012). Thus large-scale commercial operations can be opportunities for resource extraction firms to provide unskilled jobs for local residents. Unfortunately however such operations are often capital intensive and provide a small number of unskilled jobs. In fragile socio-political environments such as after a war, it is particularly important for jobs—one of the primary benefits of investment—to be distributed fairly, transparently, and without exacerbating problems and tensions that contributed to the original conflict (Hayes and Perks, 2012). Because of the often acute controversy about the relationship between large-scale extractive interests and local communities involving a wide range of tensions and conflicts, the international mining industry has in some cases been putting increasing priority on the practice of ‘community relations’. Thus some companies have begun to use community relations specialists—sociologists, communications experts, and anthropologists—to develop procedures and initiatives to respond to local community concerns (Boeg and Franks, 2012). Community relations experts try to resolve real and perceived community problems in the context of large projects, and their work focuses on increased communication, improved understanding, and stronger relationships with small-

scale stake-holders. By resolving disputes between local populations and large-scale interests, the best practice of community relations is thought to be able to reduce the risk of violent or belligerent actions such as blockades, protests, campaigns, and sabotage, particularly if small-scale extractors believe these to be the only forms of influence they can exert (Boeg and Franks, 2012).

Conclusion

The capacity of the actors and stakeholders involved in high value natural resource extraction, processing, marketing and management of revenues, is of fundamental importance in turning the curse into benefit for broader society. Such capacity however ideally needs to be balanced between stakeholders. There is a good deal of emerging evidence that ‘capacity imbalance’—whereby one set of stakeholders enjoys significant capacity while other sets experience lower and in some cases much lower capacity—can result in corruption and exploitation due to a lack of effective checks and balances between sets of stakeholders. The resulting animosity then can have profoundly negative outcomes as the lower capacity set of stakeholders realize the imbalance and its repercussions. And while capacity building in the natural resource sector is often thought of as being needed by African stakeholders (government, civil society, etc.) a great deal of capacity is lacking on the part of the international investor, who is in many cases unable to ‘read’ local socio-political and economic environments in Africa so as to be able to innovate and derive arrangements that work and are mutually beneficial. ■

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